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~Editor's Note~

Dear Readers & Contributors,

Welcome to the October 2021 issue of IJELLS.

From the references to Ramayana in the 'Adventurous Return before Lockdown' to the representation of Ravan in Annadurai's The Swooning of the God of Justice, the modern scholarship engages with the cultural encyclopaedia of Ramayana in an attempt to decode it. The papers on 'Dark Humour' and 'Gamification' are interesting to read along with the other papers.

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Happy Reading and Happy Sharing!

Dr. Mrudula Lakkaraju
Chief Editor

~ Chief Editor~

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‘Almost Ridiculous’- Dark Humor in Upamanyu Chatterjee’s *The Revenge of the Non-Vegetarian*

Rekha Karini and Rama NH Alapati

Abstract

Few critics like Mathew Winston and Brom Weber opined that the term black/dark humor has been imported from France – “*L’humor noir*” which in English translation become black humor. It functioned as a central doctrine of French surrealism almost from its inception in the 1920’s. In 1939 Andre Breton, the French surrealist writer coined the term Black humor and defined it as “a superior revolt of the mind” (xvi). It exposes the absurdity/ ridiculousness of value systems, human life, and insanities by juxtaposing melancholic elements with comical ones as is portrayed deftly in Upamanyu Chatterjee’s *The Revenge of the Non-Vegetarian*. The protagonist, Madhusudan Sen, in this novella is so blinded by vengeance, incapable of showing mercy even to a person who spent twenty-three years in prison for an act committed in anger. This study intends to explore how the author exploits dark humor in portraying the sluggishness of judicial system and prejudiced moralities over meat in *The Revenge of the Non-Vegetarian* by presenting violent or traumatic events and questions the values and perceptions of its readers.

Keywords: Dark Humor, Revenge, Murder, Non-Vegetarian Food, Judicial System, Existential Crisis

To a large extent dark/black humor can be defined as a literary mode to describe the absurdity/ ridiculousness of value systems, human life, insanities, and contradictions of modern society in which the events are often comic and painful as well. It is the humor which laughs at the ‘blacker’ sides of life like grief, despair, death, murder or insanity. Popular themes of this genre are violence, discrimination, murder, abuse, religion, war, and death, which are treated in styles that thwart the reader’s expectations of solemnity. The present study is to analyze how the novelist has exploited Dark/Black humor in portraying the class differences and sluggishness of judicial system in *The Revenge of the Non-Vegetarian*, Upamanyu Chatterjee’s seventh book. It is a novella which presents the ills of modern India like class disparities, prejudiced moralities over meat and sluggishness of judicial system with bleak and black comedy.

Though the story is set in a period between 1949 and 1973, it is timeless and relevant even to the present time. The plot of the novella is a simple linear storyline where a family of six members and their dog were burnt to death in a fire where “the flames had swallowed up the entire single-storey building and rose, with a frightful rustle and roar, fifteen feet in the air” in a town Batia, in a state called Narmada Pradesh (*The Revenge of the Non-Vegetarian*¹⁰). The novelist presents it with wit and wry narrative voice.

As the title suggests, it seems to be the revenge of the Non-vegetarian Madhusudan, ICS, on another non-vegetarian Basant Kumar Bal for killing the entire family of Nadim Dalvi. It is also the revenge of servant Basant on his master for depriving him of sustenance. It begins with the murder investigation and leads to beef politics leaving the reader to ponder over his own prejudices. The protagonist of the novella, Madhusudan Sen, an ICS officer, is the Sub-divisional Magistrate of Batia, and a connoisseur of non-vegetarian food whose typical breakfast in Calcutta consists of “eggs and sausages, liver, toast, fruit and tea”(TRNV 28). Unlike Agastya Sen, Madhusudan Sen’s son whom one has met in Chatterjee’s debut novel *English August: An Indian Story*, Madhusudan seems to be more accommodating. He says “well, frankly, I like the bungalow that’s been allotted to me, those centurial trees, those arches, that picturesque well”, to his Muslim mamlatdar Nadeem Dalvi (TRNV 35).

He lives in a “rather charming late-nineteenth-century bungalow on Temple Road in the Civil Lines area” which is part of an unofficial no-meat zone due to its proximity to Dayasagar Adinath Temple which is of great significance to the locals (TRNV 25). But he sets up a discreet method to get himself a ‘non-veg’ meal every evening through his mamlatdar. An unlikely bond forms between these two because of food. Food as the central theme, the author discusses many serious issues like beef politics and cow vigilantism. Sen, walks back daily from the magistrate’s court to his Civil Lines bungalow, followed by a glass of Cutty Sark whiskey and a single Gold Flake cigarette. He leads a dull bureaucratic life in a provincial posting, surrounded by punkhahs, peons and other eavesdropping functionaries.

Dalvi lives with his family and a dog in a huge house. Basant Kumar Bal is Dalvi’s servant who lives in the outhouse and does all the household chores like “ferrying in water and wood and coal, washing up, rushing to the bazaar to buy sugar and eggs, tending to the cows, clearing the clothesline... Never a moment’s rest for him” (TRNV 18). Although Bal is settled in Batia, he is a native of Purulia, a place he had left “on the death of his mother, some twelve years ago”, and has no family (TRNV 74). The humor of the novel darkens when Basant Kumar Bal sets fire “destroying life and property in the most inhumanly cruel manner” (TRNV 65). Max Schulz defines black humor fiction as “nontraditional” relationship to the history of novelistic storytelling (x). It “seeks . . . the comic perspective on both tragic fact and moralistic certitude” (13).

Colletta rightly points out that “Dark humour is characterized by the very concerns of Modernism. It is generally defined by ambivalence, confused chronology, plots that seem to go nowhere, and a conflicting, or even unreliable, narrative stance. It presents violent or traumatic events and questions the values and perceptions of its readers as it represents, simultaneously, the horrifying and the humorous” (2). When Basant Kumar Bal was questioned about his employers he says, “They always ate well,” (TRNV 19) and “they had non-vegetarian almost every day, saab, goat or chicken or fish or egg. They ate like rakshasas themselves and always left only two small pieces of meat in the pot, one each for the sister-in-law and her daughter” (TRNV 20). Each day after the Dalvi family has gone to bed Bal “had his dinner in the shed, whatever was left over for him by the sister-in-law and her daughter [who were treated like servants in the Dalvi house-hold] from whatever had been left over for them”(TRNV 19). Bal got only “the scrapings of the pot, some gobs of curry, some grains of rice and a couple of chapatis ... have to filch two green chillis and one raw onion to complete” his meal (TRNV 20). As he was not even given adequate food, out of anger

he murders Nadeem Dalvi and his family for an innocuous reason which seems almost ridiculous. Burton Feldman, an American professor finds that Black Humor is not audacious enough as the world outside is too worse and remarks: The truth is that Black Humor disappoints because it is not as pitilessly black or comic as it pretends to be... Far from being too audacious, Black Humor is not audacious enough for a world like ours...the world is surely worse than Black Humor is telling... (Feldman 102)

One cannot find any change in the character of Bal from the beginning to the end. The same uncertainty “that gaze of the unstable temperament hadn’t changed” in his face even after twenty-one years because a typical black humor character shows no capacity to grow or change (*TRNV* 113). He appears both ridiculous and pathetic. One laughs at him and at the same time shudder at his predicament.

As Bal murders Nadeem Dalvi’s family just for the sake of meat, an outraged Sen decides to investigate the death of his “principal protein and cholesterol supplier” and vows to turn vegetarian till justice has been done (*TRNV* 39). Also, he uses the letter of the law to close an illegal slaughterhouse, which was unknown to him, until he chanced upon the foul stench emanating from there on one of his road trips. This forces the entire town of Batia to go vegetarian as well. This shows the selfish nature of higher officials. The author portrays the present scenario of religious intolerance in our country, where people are targeted for being Muslim or eating beef.

While explaining the lengthy entwined criminal proceedings, the novelist remarks:

then you will appear before a Judicial Magistrate who will take cognizance of the crime, a charge sheet would be prepared, you’d have to spend some time in judicial custody in prison awaiting trial, and the hearing itself in the court of sessions- all that you may expect in the days- I should say years- to come. (*TRNV* 70)

After the court proceedings, Bal was put in jail with three other men who called him Gomaas Kumar as they were all vegetarians. They were kind to him and enlighten him of the delay of court proceedings where the “judges take so long to examine and take stock that it gives potatoes and other tubers enough time to grow between their Honourable toes”(*TRNV* 103-104). The author scores a brownie point in portraying the Judicial system in a darkly comical way.

When Bal was summoned to the court, he feels strange and unprotected outside the jail. The author satires the media and portrays the journalists “like stray dogs about to attack a cur who has wandered into their territory” (*TRNV* 76-77). After the trial, Bal returns to “prison in the late afternoon exhausted and afraid, less of death somehow than of living...” (*TRNV* 77) This reflects the central dilemma of black humor novels i.e., the terror of existing without reason, of wandering in the postmodern chaos. The author tries to explain the predicament of modern man who is more afraid of living than dying.

The author says the lawyers are even dirtier than a non-vegetarian’s excrement as “they suck you dry of whatever money you have” (*TRNV* 104). When Bal applies for Special Leave Petition in the Supreme Court, other prisoner says “you can sit that corner and relax and masturbate for the next four years, give or take another five” (*TRNV* 106). Also, he says

“the Supreme court will not be moved to tears by your whining” so if “I am around, we shall draft a mercy petition to the President of India. Never say die” (*TRNV* 106). The author presents the sluggishness of judicial system but doesn't hope for any reform in the system because the black humorists point out the failings of society but do not expect any change, reform or improvement in them. As Alan R Pratt, a professor, contends “Black humor involves the humorous treatment of what is grotesque, morbid, or terrifying. And while it bitterly ridicules institutions, value systems, and traditions, black humor offers neither explicit nor implicit proposals for improving, reforming, or changing the painful realities on which it focuses”(Pratt xix).

After the trial the verdict is given by Judge Shyamlal on February 7, 1956 that Bal, “heartless and satanic”, who sat down amidst the corpses to make a meal of their non-vegetarian dinner “is to be hanged by the neck till he is dead” (*TRNV* 98).According to Mathew Winston, a critic “The literature of black humor frequently depicts horrible events, unhappy people, anarchy, and chaos” (Winston, “Black Humor” 258).

Chatterjee draws a parallel between killing of animals for food, and killing of humans as a penal consequence. Sen, hovering over acceptability of death penalty, ponders over vegetarians deeming death penalty as a fit penal consequence. He asks Mr Daftari “would all vegetarians, for instance, be opposed to the death penalty for even the most despicable murderer?” (*TRNV* 89).If death penalty is acceptable, then why isn't killing of animals for food acceptable to vegetarians, and vice-versa, if death penalty is not acceptable, then why is killing of animals acceptable for non-vegetarians.

One can observe how the author draws a parallel between animals subjected to cruelty while awaiting their eventual slaughter with that of the death row convict who waits for often a decade or two until the eventuality finally dawns upon him. Also, he compares the hapless animals that grow up in closed confines, never having seen the world outside, and never knowing what it is to be like in the open, with the death row convict in the story, who is not bothered about what happens in the outside world as he is written as “not that kind of human being” (*TRNV* 74).It shows modern man's mechanical, detached outlook on life and death which is mostly reflected in black humor novels. Black humor is not only about emotional detachment from the horrors of existence; it is also about the acceptance of the historical and moral disorientation of human existence.

The author mocks the government which works only when there are some inspections or visits and remarks “the prisoners are scrubbing floors, cleaning toilets, placing potted plants in corridors and sprucing themselves up in readiness for the visit of the new Inspector General of Prisons, Madhusudan Sen” (*TRNV* 107). A death row inmate, who is seeking presidential pardon, addresses the letter to King George VI, instead to the President. “That's the template, sir, used by several dozen prisoners ever since the forties”, the subordinate informs the Inspector General and “it will serve its purpose, sir” he adds reassuringly (*TRNV* 111). No matter how grave the theme is, the novelist makes the best of it from a comic perspective.

Speaking about the delay in judicial system the author remarks, “Justice delayed is justice denied; true, but justice delayed for twenty-one years is also a gift of two decades of life to a recipient unworthy of even a moment of it” (*TRNV* 110). Sen reads the telex stating the decision of President to commute the sentence of death to imprisonment for life to Basant.

He carefully “tears the letter off the machine, all the while murmuring to himself, absentmindedly, a sort of refrain: ‘The quality of justice is not strained, the-quality-of-justice-is-not-strained’” (*TRNV* 124). He neatly rearranges the paper on the machine which looks “as though the order was never received”. Back in his room he “drinks his horrible tea” and on the way home stops “by Qayamat’s for a minute to pick up some kebabs” (*TRNV* 124). Sen’s action that may have led to the servant’s execution leaves the readers in moral turmoil.

The readers could draw the parallels in the delay of the judicial system in punishing the accused in Nirbhaya’ case and of the recent Hyderabad Disha case. In the latter case, the four accused in the rape and brutal murder of the veterinary doctor Disha were killed in an alleged ‘encounter’ early Friday morning near Shadnagar, while they were trying to flee after snatching weapons from the police. This incident has sparked a polarized debate - one side arguing that vigilantism is no substitute for due process of law; and the other citing the delay in punishing the accused in another high profile ‘Nirbhaya’ case as justification for summary ‘justice’.

With humour and a realistic representation of legal proceedings, this novella shows how a powerful, high-caste man took the life of someone he saw as an inferior to avenge the murder of another wealthy guy. Retribution that appeared to be non-vegetarian is actually privileged retaliation. Sen’s own thirst for vengeance also restricts others dietary freedom – after going vegetarian, Sen forces the entire town of Batia to follow suit by closing the abattoirs on the suggestion of a member of the temple trust.

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